

DEVELOPING CREATIVE THINKING IN FUTURE LEADERS

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Abstract. *Creative thinking is the ability to solve problems through unique and innovative approaches, generate new ideas, and introduce new perspectives into existing systems. Developing creative thinking is especially important for future leaders because modern society and the economy are changing, competitive and complex. Therefore, leaders must not only adapt to existing situations, but also be able to offer new, advanced solutions. This article examines the importance and methods of developing creative thinking in future leaders and its place in society.*

Keywords: *Creative thinking, society, ideas, economy, leadership, mentoring, strategies.*

INTRODUCTION. Like many leadership skills, creative thinking is invaluable. Future leaders can always improve their creative thinking skills, and there is always plenty of time and opportunity to get started.

First, let's look at what it means to adopt creative thinking. It's looking at something in a new way. Looking at it through a different lens or approaching a subject from a different angle. You can use creative thinking in everything from finding a new way to solve a problem to resolving conflicts at work. Giving constructive feedback is also a great way to develop creative thinking. Another example of creative thinking is using new information to give new meaning to a process.

Niels Bohr, Nobel Prize winner in physics and father of the atomic model, once said, "Prediction is very difficult, especially when it comes to the future!" It's an ironic but very true statement. Predicting the future has never been easy, but most people would agree that it's becoming increasingly difficult in today's business world, given the rapid pace of change, the blurring of boundaries between traditional industries, and the sheer volume of intelligence available. [1].

A 20-year study in developed countries has shown that creative industries create twice as many jobs as traditional ones. Despite automated work, when robots replace people, creative industries need people. As it turns out, this is a very sustainable job. The current conditions of globalization are changing the way we work and live. Today, we are increasingly faced with complex problems such as globalization, pollution, financial crises or new epidemics. Today, times are changing in such a way that in order to reach a higher level of development, it is necessary to raise a generation that is engaged in advanced technologies, nanotechnologies, and can make discoveries that will delight the world. To do this, I think, we need to change our attitude not only to young people, but also to ourselves, to get out of the influence of old skills and adapt to new values, new challenges. We should view this as a very honorable and great matter. To coordinate efforts to solve these problems, we need creative thinking and creative ideas. To develop creative qualities in a person, we must first know the meaning of this concept. Creativity is derived from the English word "create", which means "to create". Creativity is understood as a person's creative ability to create something new and solve problems. At its core lies uniqueness, practicality, unusualness and freedom. Also, creative thinking means comprehensive thinking on a particular issue, approaching one point from different angles.

Strictly speaking, today the source of success and, most importantly, personal satisfaction is not money or technology, but new ideas. The creative economy breathes new life into the production, service, trade and entertainment sectors. It changes the environment in which people want to live, work and study, as well as the environment in which they think, invent and create. The emergence of creativity as a defining element of economic life is the basis of a continuous process of change. Creativity has received its due recognition due to the growing recognition that it is a source of new technologies, new industries, new wealth and other economic advantages. For the same reason, systems have emerged aimed at stimulating and using creativity. It is precisely the pursuit of various forms of creativity that forms the deep spirit of modernity. The important features of creative work are that this work also requires internal motivation, knowledge and experience of a person and has a modern character. Currently, the following main conditions for creative problem solving are distinguished: knowledge, experience, the ability to work creatively, and personal motivation.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY. There is a lot of literature on the development of creative thinking in future leaders. Among this literature, scientific articles, textbooks, scientific literature, especially published by foreign scientists, occupy an important place. In addition, we have enough literature and textbooks in this regard in our educational program. In general, pedagogy, psychology, spirituality, philosophy, aesthetics, law, speech culture and a number of socio-humanitarian disciplines provide sufficient knowledge. Nicholas V. Kohn, Stephen M. Smith, Collaborative Fixation: The Impact of Other People's Ideas on Brainstorming, Applied Cognitive Psychology, Beau Lotto, Deviate: The Science of Seeing Differently, Creating a Sustainable Competitive Advantage, Arthur D. and other textbooks and literature on pedagogy were used on various topics on the development of creative thinking skills in individuals.

A thought or idea is a product of the creative activity of our mind. In our minds, thoughts about solutions to various problems or innovations arise. Thoughts are usually formed in the process of searching for a solution to a life problem. When thinking about a task, when facing a difficult situation, a person is forced to think. In some cases, a wonderful thought can arise in a person even without wanting to.

Creativity, as a category that develops a person, is an integral part of human thinking and spirituality. It is manifested not in the versatility of the knowledge possessed by a person, but in the pursuit of new ideas, in reforming and changing established stereotypes, in making unexpected and unusual decisions in the process of solving life problems. That is, creativity cannot be achieved by repeating the given knowledge, the main condition is the emergence of a new thought, a new idea in the process of creative thinking. For example, even if you memorize English words and "drink up" grammar rules, if you can't write an essay, it's all for naught.

That is why imagination plays an important role in the creative thinking process. This is exactly what Albert Einstein meant when he said, "Imagination is more important than knowledge." Often, unusual ideas and solutions come to a person unexpectedly. To do this, first of all, the monotony and routine in the thinking process must be eliminated.

The human brain uses patterns and stereotypes to "facilitate" and "convenient" its work. Stereotypes are previously known and generally accepted ideas. Thinking based on them does not give us any new ideas. The social thought that prevails in society, as well as the forms and manifestations presented in media products, also play a leading role in the emergence of patterns.

A person agrees with everyone's opinion in order not to stand out from the crowd. In addition, "going with the flow" seems easier than independent thinking. When thinking through stereotypes, when a person's mind is "asked" about a certain topic, typical information and judgments arise.

It is true that the influence of creative thinking is behind significant types of innovation in society as a whole, but it is also a phenomenon of universal and equalizing nature, that is, any person, to one degree or another, has the ability to think creatively. American scientist D. Wexler defines creativity as a type of thinking that requires a person to come up with several solutions to a problem or issue at once and, unlike stereotyped, boring thinking, helps to understand the uniqueness and uniqueness of the essence of things and phenomena.

Creativity, by further improving a person's thinking ability, acts as the supreme director of social life and human activity, directing it towards noble deeds. Such a creative person always acts in harmony with existence. French philosopher Henri Bergson recognizes "Creativity as the highest stage of intelligence."

❖ Leaders who develop creative thinking are effective in implementing changes in society and organizations, creating new opportunities, and solving problems in innovative ways. To develop new ideas and innovations, leaders must have the following skills:

❖ Solving problems with innovative approaches: Creative thinking helps leaders find new, innovative solutions to problems.

❖ Adapting quickly to changing conditions: Creative thinking allows leaders to quickly adapt to global and local changes.

❖ Effective resource management: Creative thinking allows leaders to use resources effectively and create new opportunities.

❖ Highly motivated and inspired: Creative thinking inspires the leader and his team with new ideas [2].

The creative potential of the teacher. In order to teach students to think creatively and to form creative thinking in them, the teacher must first of all be a creative and creative person. If he himself does not have the qualities of creativity, then how can he encourage students to think creatively? The only conclusion that can be drawn is as follows: only if the teacher himself is creative and creative, the students can be like that. It is not necessary for the teacher to be creative and creative or not, but to organize lessons in the spirit of creativity and creativity, to strive to try out new ideas in the educational process.

In the lessons, the teacher moves along the following four directions according to the "creativity roadmap", and the actions in them are considered signs of the creativity of teachers (Patti Drepreau): 1) demonstration of creative thinking skills; 2) ability to use strategies (methods and tools) that encourage students to master academic subjects with interest; 3) innovative approaches and creative approaches to finding solutions to pedagogical issues (problems); 4) expected result 5. Structural foundations and priority principles of creative potential. The creative potential of a teacher is reflected as his general characteristic. It is considered the initial condition and result of creative activity.

This quality expresses the ability and readiness of a person to express himself. In addition, the creative potential is based on the integral manifestation of the personal abilities, natural and social potential of each specialist. Creative potential is closely related to creativity directed at the process of cognition. The creative potential of a teacher, unlike traditional thinking, is manifested in the following: - speed and flexibility of thinking; - the ability to create new ideas; - not to think

in a stereotyped way; - originality; - initiative; - tolerance of uncertainty; - intelligence. In order for a teacher to have creative potential, he must pay attention to the following in his professional activities: - a creative approach to his professional activities; - showing activity in creating new ideas; - independent study of advanced pedagogical achievements and experiences; exchange of ideas with colleagues on pedagogical achievements.

There are several ways to develop creative thinking in future leaders:

1. The Education and Training Process.

The most effective way to teach creative thinking begins with the educational process. To teach creative thinking to future leaders:

✚ Interactive teaching methods: It is necessary to teach students not only to acquire knowledge, but also to create their own ideas, to solve problems with new approaches.

✚ Project-based learning: Students need to work on real-life problems to put their ideas into practice.

✚ Creative teachers and mentors: Teachers and mentors need to use their own advanced methods to teach creative thinking to their students [3].

2. Experience and Practice

✚ Creating practical experience and testing new ideas is essential for developing creative thinking. This can be done in the following ways for future leaders:

✚ Experimenting and trying out innovations: Leaders should not be afraid to introduce new ideas and technologies. Experience is gained by trying new ideas.

✚ Learning from mistakes: The process of creative thinking involves learning from mistakes. Every mistake can be the basis for creating new opportunities.

3. Teamwork and Collaboration

✚ Teamwork is essential for the effective development of creative thinking. Future leaders must learn to integrate different ideas, perspectives, and approaches:

✚ Cross-functional teams: Collaborating with people from different disciplines helps leaders generate new ideas.

✚ Discussion and brainstorming: New approaches emerge through team discussion and brainstorming.

4. Openness to New Technologies

✚ The development of creative thinking depends on understanding and effectively using modern technologies. Future leaders should be open to new technologies and apply them in their work [4]:

✚ Learning digital technologies: Learning innovative technologies, such as artificial intelligence, data analytics, and other advanced tools, helps leaders create new solutions.

✚ Applying technological innovations: New technologies can effectively solve problems in society and the economy [5].

5. The Role of Creative Thinking in Society

✚ Developing the creative thinking skills of future leaders contributes to the overall development of society. Through creative thinking:

✚ Economic innovation: Future leaders will have the opportunity to develop new industries, create innovative products, and modernize the economy.

✚ Social sustainability: With the help of creative thinking, social systems can be improved and problems in society can be solved.

 Political innovation: Creative leaders can develop new political strategies and laws and adapt them to the needs of society [6].

The first stage in the formation of future leaders is education and training. High-quality education and professional development play an important role in the formation of leadership qualities of a leader. To become a leader in society, not only academic knowledge, but also practical skills are needed. Leaders must know various methods and techniques to achieve their social and business goals, have the ability to think logically and analyze when making decisions. At the same time, leaders must master modern management techniques, which include innovative thinking and adaptability to a rapidly changing environment.

Informatization of education is a process aimed at providing the educational sphere with modern information and communication technologies and technical means in a methodological and practical way and implementing the psychological and pedagogical goals of the educational process based on their effective use.

Creative qualities of a teacher: developing children's educational activities, positive qualities. At the same time, it directs them to independent upbringing and mastering knowledge. For creative thinking, teachers should develop professional activity from their student years.

They should work hard on themselves, direct themselves to creative activity, and analyze problem situations. One of the most popular types of pedagogical technologies today is interactive methods. Interactive methods are joint activities of the student and the teacher, which mainly encourage students to think. As a means of developing creative abilities, a number of authors offer methods designed to exercise creative imagination on the basis of various materials. In particular, in the exercises proposed in the practical manuals of Ye.P. Rogov, which are intended to be carried out in a group format, for example, one of the training participants can pose a question with a fantastic situation (for example, the question "What changes would occur in life on Earth if people could read each other's minds?"), and the rest of the group members can be given the task of formulating their own answers as colorfully as possible.

B. Clegg has developed a unique intensive course on the development of creative thinking, the basis of which is tasks designed to analyze what associations are evoked by objects and phenomena that are not normally found in the indicated unit (for example, what are the bases of units such as "ice cream with a spike", "teapot with a hat", "chef in an aquarium", "cellar on the roof").

E. de Bono, a world-renowned expert in the field of developing methodological foundations for developing non-standard thinking, suggests that the "provocative idea" methodology is an effective method for putting forward an incredible, illogical idea (for example, "car wheels should be square"), avoiding its evaluation and continuing to develop it. According to the author, if "provocative" ideas are allowed to be evaluated, thinking immediately rejects them due to their inconsistency with existing standards in experience. For the development of creative thinking, instead of evaluating such ideas and determining how much they fit into the boundaries of personal experience, it is necessary to achieve a transition to new ideas arising from these ideas. The process of transition from unusual ideas to new ideas, according to E. de Bono, consists in finding a useful solution from these illogical ideas and coming to some logically reasonable conclusion.

As can be seen from the above brief analysis, most of the methodological tools intended to develop creative thinking consist of tasks that require a creative approach from a person. Here we

are witnessing a situation analogous to the approach in exercises and trainings that serve to develop various cognitive processes or communicative skills. As is known, in most of this category of practical training, tasks and assignments are in the content of activating the relevant process. For example, the recommendation to use the proofreading test methodology for correctional and developmental purposes is based on the fact that, according to the terms of the task, a person is forced to concentrate his attention in a specific area, limited by the distracting influence of the environment, in order to identify a form that does not stand out clearly against a uniform background.

CONCLUSION. Creative thinking is not only an important skill for future leaders, but also a key tool for the development of society. Through education, experience, teamwork, and openness to technology, leaders can develop creative thinking. This, in turn, helps to implement innovative ideas, economic growth, social stability, and political innovations in society. Developing creative thinking is an important condition for the success of future leaders and for leading society in progressive directions.

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